

CHANGE DETECTION USING SYNTHETIC HYPERSPECTRAL IMAGERY

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ABSTRACT

In the best of circumstances, change detection (CD) is accomplished using measurements from the same instrument and under similar collection circumstances. Complications in the CD process arise when the variability in the collection process is not minimized. Variations between collected images and a lack of precise corresponding ground truth make accurate evaluation of a given CD method imprecise at best. This work leverages synthetic hyperspectral imagery, with known ground truth to include primary and tertiary materials, to investigate the use of common CD algorithms for the hyperspectral CD problem. Specifically, we use synthetic hyperspectral images with different spatial resolutions acquired at different altitudes, thus exhibiting different atmospheric affects. The importance of this work is in definition of a CD taxonomy and using that taxonomy for the accurate evaluation of several CD methods. Results are presented using receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves and the area under the ROC curve, indicating that, under mildly varying imaging conditions, principal component analysis-based CD outperforms simple image differencing and correlation coefficient-based CD methods.

Index Terms— Change detection, hyperspectral

1. INTRODUCTION

Hyperspectral (HS) change detection (CD) is an important component to numerous scientific and engineering disciplines. Its use spans a myriad of applications to include assessment of forest fuels as a function of time, analysis of post fire reforestation progress, and more recently for the detection of moving objects in a target tracking scenario, to name a few. The ability to accurately assess the quality of the CD method is at the heart of success for such applications.

CD in simple terms, is an algorithm that generates a change mask based upon temporal changes between two or more measurements. The goal of CD system is to identify changes important to the end user. However, differences

resulting from variations in the acquisition sensor or the environment can cause unwanted false alarms.

In an ideal CD system, the temporal images would be acquired by the same instrument where the resultant images have the same spatial and spectral properties. In the case of HS change detection, spectral differences between sensors requires additional work to resolve. Real world constraints often dictate the use of different sensors and collection conditions. Issues such as inferring spatial resolution from imaging altitude, along with variations in atmospheric conditions can alter scene characteristics and thus must be considered when doing an end-to-end CD process. Ultimately, accurate CD depends on the ability to successfully relate differences in corrected measurements to actual changes of interest. As such, image-based differences need to be resolved before examining real changes. The correction of these inherent and differing image characteristics is a crucial process to the CD scheme and represents a major component of any CD taxonomy.

This work presents a CD taxonomy, detailing the preprocessing component of the process, and evaluates CD methods based on that taxonomy. Synthetic data is used order to gain an understanding of how the CD method performs on data collected under differing collection conditions. Due to knowledge of primary and tertiary materials contained in each hyperspectral pixel, accurate receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves and area under the ROC curve (AUC) can be generated. The use of the synthetic HS data allows one to gain a better understanding of true end-to-end system performance as a function of induced system, environmental, and collection conditions.

2. METHODOLOGY

Although other taxonomies of a CD system may exist, we present our view of the taxonomy in Fig. 1. The taxonomy includes three phases: preprocessing, change detection, and assessment. Each of the three phases is discussed in detail in the following sections.

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Fig. 1. A change detection taxonomy.

2.1. Preprocessing

CD is complex process where the detection results are influenced by several factors. Significant variance in spatial, spectral, and radiometric resolutions for a set of temporal imagery can hinder the success of the CD process.

Environmental characteristics encountered during acquisition must be accounted for to ensure effective CD. These characteristics include atmospheric conditions and vegetation phonological characteristics. Atmospheric effects are particularly important and need to be corrected to ensure proper image comparability [1]. A full radiometric correction supported by measurements of several atmospheric parameters taken during acquisition would result in a robust atmospheric correction process. Unfortunately this method is time consuming, computationally intensive, and subject to variation in the results to uncertainty in atmospheric parameter estimation. Due to its simplicity and wide acceptance in the remote sensing community, the empirical line method (ELM) is used. Since it is a linear mapping, it is only capable of accounting for linear affects. As such, any nonlinear affects are not accounted for.

CD is one of many applications where it is a necessity to perform joint analysis on a set of imagery of a similar scene acquired at different times. Given two images, a reference image and a sensed image, the goal is to match the sensed image (assumed in this case to be the low-resolution image) to the reference images pixel coordinate system making corresponding coordinate points in the two images fit the same geographical location. This process is called image matching [2]. Image matching can be difficult because for a given point in the reference image, a corresponding point may not exist in the matching image due to occlusion or differences in GSD. Furthermore, there may be more than one possible match due to repetitive patterns. In these cases, additional knowledge may be required to resolve the problem.

CD methods are sensitive to registration errors. A part of

the misregistration error is attributed to image interpolation in the registration process. Dai and Khorram [3] document the effects of image misregistration on CD by simulating the misregistration process articulating that interpolation induces registration error. In our registration process, we use the results from coincident image matching to resample the image with the lowest GSD. Resampling occurs from high resolution to low resolution since it may be less meaningful to “create” information as could be considered the case when going from low-resolution to high-resolution. Resampling can be accomplished by any number of interpolation methods to include bilinear, nearest neighbor, cubic spline, and others. Each method may have a different affect on the outcome, but is not studied here. In this study, the nearest neighbor resampling method is used due to computational efficiency.

Linear image enhancement methods can be used to help alleviate potential inconsistencies between images. These linear enhancement methods are often necessary to address differences, such as intensity changes at the pixel level, as they are not often changes one would want to detect [4]. Common inconsistencies include differences in surface conditions, illumination geometry, and sensors. These error sources can be reduced using methods such as spectral normalization or covariance equalization. In this work, spectra are not normalized.

2.2. Change Detection

Many documented CD techniques are applicable to remote sensed multi-temporal data sets. The CD algorithms implemented in this paper include absolute image differencing, principal component analysis (PCA), and a modified correlation coefficient (MCC).

The absolute difference of two images with equal dimensions is created by taking the absolute value of the pixel-by-pixel difference between the reference and sensed images. The PCA approach accepts the reference and sensed images as input and reorganizes them via a linear transformation such that the output images are linearly independent. In CD studies, the consequence of this linearization is that unchanged pixels, or common information shared by a pair of images, are expected to lie in a narrow elongated cluster along a principal axis equivalent to the first principal component (PC1). On the contrary, pixels containing a change would be more unique in their spectral appearance and would be expected to lie on a different axis (PC2). The modified correlation coefficient uses a maximum likelihood estimate of the change parameter incorporated in the joint conditional probability density function (PDF) of an image pair [5].

2.3. Assessment & Evaluation

The receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve and the area under the ROC curve (AUC) methods are used in this

work to evaluate system performance. The ROC curve plots probability of detection (P_D) against the probability of false alarm (P_{FA}) giving one a method to compare systems along a range of operating conditions. In the case one is after an “average” feel, the AUC summarizes the ROC curve by estimating the area under each curve.

3. SYNTHETIC HYPERSPECTRAL DATA

The Digital Imaging and Remote Sensing Image Generation (DIRSIG) model is used to generate the synthetic hyperspectral imagery used in this study. DIRSIG enables one to generate synthetic scenes that can span the spectra of 0.3-20 μ m and encompass an array of spatial and spectral phenomena [6]. The sensors spectral characteristics can be specified and the spatial calculated based on platform altitude and acquisition angle. The dataset mimics an AVIRIS-like sensor (224 bands ranging from 0.36 to 2.55 μ m). Two images were generated, the reference image (Fig. 2(a)) at 10Kft mean sea level (MSL) and the sensed image (Fig. 2(b)) at 40Kft MSL with a computed GSD of 0.29m and 1.21m respectively.

Fig. 2. DIRSIG test images at 10Kft and 40Kft mean sea level with 0.29m and 1.21m GSD’s respectively.

The two scenes are identical with the exception of the location of three vehicles of interest: a blue pickup truck, a soiled green sedan, and a clean white sport utility vehicle. The changes one hopes to detect are the positional changes of the vehicles and four in-scene fiducials. The vehicles are scattered in the first image in an open intersection, partly-occluded by a tree canopy, and adjacent to a tree line. The vehicles are processed to unite along a road in the open prior to the second pass. The fiducials are comprised of white and black panels which have a precise (and known) center aiding in spectral calibration spatial registration of the images.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Preprocessing

The first phase includes the generation of the imagery coincident with two time periods in which change has transpired and the preprocessing of the data. Atmospheric correction converts the image of sensor reaching radiance to estimated

reflectance. As stated previously, this is accomplished using ELM.

Fiducials were used as GCPs to perform image-to-image registration to image match the data sets. Next we performed nearest neighbor interpolation to account for the varying GSD’s between the referenced and sensed images to establish a common coordinate system while preserving information in the imagery. The lower GSD image (higher spatial resolution) was interpolated to the higher GSD image (lower spatial resolution). The preprocessing results are displayed in Fig. 3(a) and Fig. 3(b) for the reference (10Kft MSL) and sensed (40Kft MSL) images respectively.

(a) Post processed 10K image (b) Post processed 40K image

Fig. 3. Post processed DIRSIG test images. (a) The 10Kft MSL image is resampled using the nearest neighbor method to match the GSD of the 40Kft MSL image. (b) The 40Kft MSL image is matched to the spatially down-sampled 10Kft MSL image.

4.2. Change Detection

The second phase involves finding important changes apparent between the sensed and referenced images. True differences, as determined by considering primary and tertiary material content of each image pixel, are shown in Fig. 4(a). The results of the CD processes are compared to this truth image.

In the image differencing method, the absolute difference of the same frequency bands were “change processed” to result in a single cube structure. The summation of the band differences is shown in Fig. 4(b).

The results obtained from PCA-based CD are presented in Fig. 4(c). This method results in two image cubes after processing, where the second cube corresponds to PC2 reflecting the change results (and displayed). PCA shows results visually similar to those of the image differencing method.

The MCC algorithm uses a 3×3 pixel sliding window when searching for band-to-band changes. The MCC results are shown in Fig. 4(d), which is the sum of all band changes between the reference and sensed image cubes.

4.3. Assessment

To validate the change maps, the third phase involves performance assessment to report the quality of the results. A

Fig. 4. Truth map and change detection results between the 10Kft and 40Kft MSL images. (a) Truth image of changes derived from the synthetic hyperspectral imagery. (b) Results for image differencing. (c) Results for principal component analysis (PCA). (d) Results for the modified correlation coefficient (MCC).

CD Method	AUC
Image Differencing	0.8946
PCA	0.8982
MCC	0.7409

Table 1. Area Under the ROC Curve (AUC) Results

ROC curve based on the truth map in Fig. 4(a) is produced for each algorithm and shown in Fig 5(b-d). The ROC curves illustrate three distinct operating regions of interest. Image differencing performs better for ($P_{FA} < 0.2$), PCA for ($0.2 \geq P_{FA} < 0.75$), and MCC for ($P_{FA} > 0.75$). The performance of PCA compared to image differencing is not as cut and dry. Considering the AUC values presented in Table 1, one may conclude that PCA has only slightly better average performance compared Image Differencing.

5. SUMMARY & CONCLUSION

One objective of this study was to provide a taxonomy for CD and use that taxonomy to address HS CD. Three CD methods are evaluated on synthetic HS data where absolute truth is known, enabling an accurate empirical examination and quantitative assessment of each approach. Traditional preprocessing techniques were utilized as part of this taxonomy.

In an effort to evaluate difference CD methods, synthetic HS imagery was used. The power of such data is that all conditions are controllable, and one may generate data specific to

Fig. 5. ROC curves for all three CD methods: image difference (solid), PCA (dotted), and MCC (dashed)

the study of interest. Isolated studies are important in order to understand how different instruments, environment conditions, and preprocessing techniques affect the CD process.

Finally, an extension to the CD taxonomy may include a *Post processing* block between the *Change Detection* and *Assessment* blocks of Fig. 1 to correct for small misclassified area caused by edge effects resulting from registration, or other errors induced by the preprocessing stage.

6. REFERENCES

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